

The Attitude Toward Using E-commerce for Beauty Products: The Role of Usefulness and Ease of Use

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Abstract— With an emphasis on Shopee in Indonesia, this study investigates how consumers' purchase intentions are affected by Augmented Reality (AR)-based Virtual Try-On technology. While Shopee leads the cosmetic e-commerce market, issues such as product mismatches remain a challenge. What makes this study unique is its context-specific examination of AR adoption within the beauty product segment of an emerging market, where the integration of immersive technologies in online retail is still developing. Utilizing a quantitative research approach, information was gathered via an online survey and 352 valid responses analyzed using SmartPLS. The results reveal significant positive relationships between purchase intention, attitude toward utilizing AR, as well as its perceived utility and usability. The results offer useful recommendations for e-commerce platforms to refine AR features that enhance interactivity, visualization accuracy, and decision-making support. Future applications of this research include extending AR use to other product categories, assessing its long-term effects on brand loyalty and repeat purchases, and exploring cross-cultural adoption patterns to optimize AR integration for diverse consumer segments.

Keywords—Augmented Reality, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Toward Using, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growth of e-commerce has been swift worldwide, with consumer behavior being transformed and market dynamics being impacted. In Indonesia, Shopee has emerged as the most visited e-commerce platform [1], attracting 237 million visits in September 2023, representing a 38% increase in traffic since the beginning of the year [2]. This expansion strengthens Shopee's position as the leading online marketplace, especially in the beauty product category [3]. According to the survey, Shopee is the most influential platform for selling beauty products in Indonesia, with 98% of respondents claiming to have purchased cosmetics through the website [4].

One constant problem with online shopping is that what consumers expect and what they actually buy, becomes a persistent barrier [5]. Virtual Try-On, a technology that uses Augmented Reality (AR) to enable consumers to digitally preview products before purchase, has been developed as redefining the issue [6]. AR is integrated into Virtual Try-On, enabling users to interact and experience immersive product visualizations [7]. By analyzing user preferences, such as skin tone in the cosmetics industry, Artificial Intelligence (AI) can improve personalization. This technology makes it seem as though the virtual world is integrated with reality, adding

realism and consumer confidence. Originally adopted in industrial applications, such as Boeing's production processes in the 1990s [7], AR has since been integrated into consumer-facing platforms, including Shopee's Virtual Try-On feature in the beauty category.

The Technology adoption Model (TAM) is used in this study to examine the factors that influence consumers' adoption of virtual try-on technology [8]. Perceived Utility (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), two fundamental TAM construct, along with related factors such as media richness and enjoyment, have been shown to influence purchase intention [9][10][11]. Yet, Indonesia's moderate level of digital literacy presents potential adoption barriers [12]. Therefore, ensuring the accessibility and user-friendliness of Virtual Try-On is critical for enhancing consumer engagement, trust, and purchase behavior [3].

The purpose of the study is to assess how AR-based virtual try-ons affect customers' inclinations to buy within beauty e-commerce, focusing on Shopee as the research context [6]. By employing the TAM framework, this study investigates how PU and PEOU shape Attitude Toward Using (ATU) and, subsequently, Purchase Intention (PI). Furthermore, it explores the factors that may strengthen the connection between PU and PEOU, highlighting the part digital literacy and intuitive interface design in fostering AR adoption [10].

While prior studies have largely concentrated on AR's direct impact on purchase intention in beauty e-commerce, this research advances the field by explicitly addressing potential long-term behavioral impacts, such as repeat purchases, sustained engagement, and brand loyalty [13][14]. This perspective on post-purchase behavior has been underexplored in emerging markets, providing a basis for more sustainable AR adoption strategies. Additionally, the study offers practical recommendations for integrating AR features with customer retention programs, enabling e-commerce platforms to transform Virtual Try-On from a novelty tool into a strategic driver of customer lifetime value.

Through its focus on Indonesia's beauty e-commerce sector and its extension of TAM analysis to include both present and future consumer behavior, this research merges theory and practice by demonstrating how AR can serve as a catalyst for brand-consumer relationships in rapidly expanding digital economies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A systematic method was used to identify, evaluate, and summarize previous studies on virtual simulations utilizing

Shopee's Virtual Try-On technology with Augmented Reality (AR) [8]. Its focus is on identifying the factors that influence the adoption of virtual try-on clients, and this study builds upon their understanding of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Attitude Toward Using (ATU) is the factor that influences Purchase Intention, which is dependent on both perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU). The other variable.

A. AR Perceived Usefulness

According to TAM, a user's perception of perceived usefulness is indicative only of how much new technology would help them complete tasks more efficiently [1][15]. Research conducted earlier has consistently demonstrated that consumer buying tendencies are influenced by their perceptions of a system's efficiency [1]. This implies that the perceived benefits of a system have essentially the same significance to an individual as those systems themselves.

Accordingly, Perceived Usefulness was chosen as a major variable in this study [16]. It is measured using four indicators: saving time, assisting with knowledge retrieval, enhancing productivity, and boosting job performance [15][16][17]. These indicators were used to assess perceived usability factors [18]. Prior findings indicate that integrating AR features into Shopee's e-commerce platform can simplify the process of purchasing cosmetics online without requiring excessive effort to learn the technology [4][14][19].

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Attitude Toward Using E-Commerce is significantly improved by AR Perceived Usefulness.

B. AR Perceived Ease of Use

The degree to which a person thinks that utilizing a technology would be effortless is known as perceived ease of use and will enhance their ability to accomplish online shopping goals effectively and efficiently [16]. Four assertions are used to gauge it: easy to use, clear and simple to understand, easy to master, and simple to learn [17][18].

When perceived ease of use is high, it means that consumers feel confident in operating and understanding the technology without feeling overwhelmed [18][20]. Empirical evidence shows that consumers are more likely to purchase products through virtual product trials when the feature is perceived as easy to operate, particularly in selecting cosmetics [19][21][22].

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Attitude Toward Using E-Commerce is significantly improved by AR Perceived Ease of Use.

C. Attitude Toward Using

Attitude Toward Using acts as a mediating variable that reflects how consumers respond when engaging with new technologies such as AR in e-commerce [18]. The response may be positive (acceptance) or negative (rejection), depending on the perceived outcomes of use. A positive attitude arises when users experience favorable results from interacting with the system, indicating a belief in its usefulness [13][21][23]. Over time, such experiences can lead to habitual usage [14].

Attitudes characterized as practical, enjoyable, optimistic, and engaging demonstrate interest in the application, which can influence online shopping behavior [17]. Furthermore, customer satisfaction has a substantial impact on shaping purchase intentions [3][7][10][20].

Hypothesis 3 (H3): In e-commerce, Purchase Intention is significantly positively impacted by Attitude Toward Using.

D. Purchase Intention

The willingness of a customer to purchase goods or services is referred to as purchase intention, which arises from evaluations of AR-enabled online shopping experiences [4][6][8]. It is influenced by several factors, including positive attitudes toward technology use, perceived benefits, virtual presence, interactivity, and appreciation of AR capabilities [14].

Website usability perceptions affect purchase likelihood [24], and consumers also value the benefits obtained by utilizing the AR Virtual Try-On function [3][18][25]. Purchase intentions are significantly influenced by the perceived advantages and simplicity of use of AR interaction [7][14][20].

The research hypothesis model depicted in Fig. 1 presents the links between Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Toward Using, and Purchase Intention that were examined in this study.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): In e-commerce, Purchase Intention is significantly positively impacted by Perceived Usefulness.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): In e-commerce, Purchase Intention is significantly positively impacted by perceived ease of use.

Fig. 1. Hypothesis Model for Purchase Intention to E-commerce

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A quantitative research approach was used in this study to examine the relationships between variables that may exhibit causal associations. The indicators used to measure each construct are listed in Table I, titled Indicators of Variables. The research utilized primary data collected directly from Shopee users in Indonesia who Using the AR Virtual Try-On functionality, with a particular focus on beauty product consumers.

TABLE I. INDICATORS OF VARIABLES

NO	Variables	Indicators
1	AR Perceived Usefulness [18]	Saving time
		Helping to find information
		Improving work performance
		Increasing productivity
2	AR Perceived Ease of Use [18]	Simple to learn
		Clear and easy to grasp
		Easy to master
		Easy to use
3	Attitude Toward Using [17]	Good
		Sensible
		Enjoyable
		Upbeat
		Captivating ideas

4	Purchase Intention to E-commerce [14]	Positive attitudes toward technology use
		Advantages
		Virtual presence (product presence)
		Interactivity
		Consumer appreciation of AR capabilities

A systematic questionnaire made with Google Forms was used to collect data distributed digitally. A five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting strongly disagree and 5 denoting strongly agree, was used throughout the survey's twenty-four items. A total of 352 legitimate answers were gathered. The majority of respondents selected a score of 4, indicating a generally high level of agreement with the questionnaire statements.

Using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method and SmartPLS software, data analysis was carried out. Testing direct hypotheses and assessing the structural model (inner model) were part of the investigation. The inner model was evaluated to ascertain the framework's dependability and capacity for explanation. The exogenous variables' percentage of variation in the endogenous variables was assessed using the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R²). Explanatory power is considered strong when the R² value is 0.75 or above, moderate when it is around 0.50, and weak when it is around 0.25.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

352 people in all took part in the survey, which was made available using Google Forms. 95.1% of responders were female, compared to 4.9% who were male. 18–22 years old made up the largest age group (44.7%), followed by 23–27 years old (33.2%) and those above 27 (22.1%). In terms of socioeconomic background, 55.5% identified as upper class, 30% as middle class, and 14.5% as lower class. The highest concentration of respondents was in the DKI Jakarta and West Java regions.

Fig. 2. Bootstrapping Model Results

TABLE II. DIRECT HYPOTHESIS TESTING RESULTS

	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Status
ARPEU → ATU	0.067	6.759	0.000	Approve
ARPEU → PI	0.087	2.317	0.021	Approve
ARPU → ATU	0.072	5.195	0.000	Approve
ARPU → PI	0.072	3.251	0.001	Approve
ATU → PI	0.067	6.691	0.000	Approve

The data, analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in SmartPLS, is presented in Fig. 2 and Table II. All

research variables met the validity and reliability requirements, with significance levels below 0.05.

A. Perceived Usefulness Through Attitude Toward Using

A strong relationship was identified between AR Perceived Usefulness (ARPU) and Attitude Toward Using (ATU), having a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 5.195 (> 1.96), suggesting that the hypothesis is supported. Shopee users reported that ARPU improves decision-making processes, optimizes time usage, provides a pleasant shopping experience, enables more accurate cosmetic selection, and reduces purchase errors.

The positive influence of PU on ATU can be explained by several relevant aspects, especially when utilizing Augmented Reality (AR) technology for purchasing beauty products. AR enables consumers to virtually simulate product use without the need for physical trials. This eliminates the necessity of visiting stores and significantly reduces the time spent on product comparisons. The feature also enhances interactivity, creating a more engaging shopping experience that fosters positive emotional responses toward the technology.

Additionally, AR's ability to provide accurate and personalized visual information increases user confidence in selecting products that match their preferences, while minimizing the risk of purchase errors. Integrating AR with personalized recommendation systems can further enhance trust, accelerate decision-making, and improve conversion rates. More effective product evaluations are achieved by providing detailed, personalized information that builds trust in the e-commerce platform. Hence, the more evidence there is of real benefits gained from using AR, then the greater are prospects for using this technology in online beauty stores [18].

B. Perceived Ease of Use Through Attitude Toward Using

Its hypothesis was substantiated by a significant correlation between ATU, Attitude Toward Using, and AR Perceived Ease of Use, with p-value $> / 0.05$ and statistical significance = 6.759 ($p + 1.96$). Consumers are interested in modern technology that's easy to use, and the presence of simpler system designs boosts interest in adoption. The ease of use is a significant factor in determining user adoption when new technology is introduced.

The ease of use, or PEU, is a significant factor in how consumers perceive new technologies like Augmented Reality (AR) when purchasing beauty products. This is particularly important. A smooth and intuitive interface contributes to user comfort, while also reducing the feeling of being overwhelmed. A basic design enables users to quickly grasp how the technology works without having to spend a lot of time learning it. By facilitating the purchase of beauty products online, customers can try on various products at their leisure.

The reduction of technical barriers through PEU enhances user confidence and creates a sense of control, which in turn increases the likelihood of consumers making purchases. To ensure high adoption rates, Shopee exemplifies the importance of both usability testing and interface optimization, as well as feature development. Appearances towards AR tend to be more positive when the virtual try-on experience meets user expectations in a fast-paced, seamless digital world. The beauty industry's ease of use allows consumers to compare products, conduct product tests, and make informed decisions,

which strengthens their purchase intentions. Previous studies in the same field have also yielded similar results [18].

C. Attitude Toward Using Toward Purchase Intention

The conclusion that the hypothesis is valid was reached through a significant relationship between Attitude (ATU) and Purchase Intention (PI), with both measures having p-value of 0.010 (0.01), and t-statistics of 1.96 being positive. Shopee recidivers were pleased with the service, reporting that it made them feel at ease, entertained and confident about their technology. The influence of ATU on PI is evident from these factors.

The findings suggest that a positive perception of the platform is essential in influencing consumer behavior when it comes to buying beauty items. The technology is deemed trustworthy, as users who are satisfied with the platform and its services are more likely to use it, leading to increased confidence in their purchases. By offering a straightforward and uncomplicated user interface, the clear design and easy-to-use navigation enhances satisfaction and encourages more frequent beauty product purchases. The platform's ease of use and enjoyment contribute to the creation of a positive mindset, which can lead to increased purchases.

Value and practicality, particularly in providing personalized shopping experiences and convenience, enhance user engagement and encourage them to purchase beauty items. The use of personalized recommendations for makeup, skincare, or cosmetic tools boosts confidence in making purchases. The presence of social media, whether it's positive feedback or product endorsement ratings, can boost trust and encourage more purchases on the site. A positive mindset helps users feel more secure when shopping for beauty products online, as it makes them feel safer.

The outcomes indicate that a strong Attitude Toward Using significantly impacts Purchase Intention, particularly when the platform promotes trust, simplicity, and enjoyment in the cosmetic purchase process. Additionally, These findings, which are in line with earlier studies in the same field [17].

D. Perceived Usefulness Toward Purchase Intention

A significant correlation was observed between ARPU and PI, leading to a support for the hypothesis. The p-value of 0.001 (0.05) and our test's t-statistics of 1.96 were positive. According to Shopee users, PU aids in making decisions, boosts buyer confidence and offers practical and sensible benefits. Additionally,

The study indicates that the impact of PU on PI is substantial. Why? Users are aware that the platform's usefulness supports informed decision-making, increases confidence in product choices, and provides tangible benefits.... The purchase process is made more efficient and convenient with PU, which provides clear and reliable information. When the platform provides users with clear advantages, such as relevant product recommendations and valuable information, they are more likely to trust the system and consider it a useful tool for future transactions. The presence of easy-to-use navigation and intuitive design enhances this impression, thereby driving shoppers towards purchases.

PU has an extremely strong effect in the beauty industry. Why? With the website, customers can compare different options and read detailed reviews to boost their confidence in

selecting from various products. Personalization can be further encouraged through the use of platforms that tailor recommendations based on skin tone and purchase history. The practical benefits of PU are beneficial for increasing purchase motivation, especially in the fiercely competitive beauty markets where personalized experiences and trustworthiness are crucial. These results, which are in line with earlier studies in this domain [7].

E. Perceived Ease of Use Toward Purchase Intention

Purchase Intention (PI) and AR Perceived Ease of Use (ARPEU) were shown to be significantly correlated, with a p-value of 0.021 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 2.317 (> 1.96), confirming that the hypothesis is supported. PEU contributes to user-friendliness, enhances usability, is easy to understand, is straightforward and clear, aligns with user habits, matches user behavior, and fosters a sense of comfort and confidence when adopting new technologies.

Users consider PEU to be an improvement on the platform's navigation, making it easier and more accessible. The convenience boosts confidence in the platform and provides a more comfortable and enjoyable shopping experience, especially with the integration of new technologies like Augmented Reality (AR) for beauty products. A platform that's user-centric and engages users, promotes consistent engagement, and generates more purchases. The simplicity of the system reduces concerns about using new tools, fostering trust and comfort in the shopping process.

In the beauty market, this ease of use allows users to experiment with products virtually, compare them according to individual preferences, and make informed decisions without the limitations of traditional shopping. This leads to an intuitive, seamless experience increasing the willingness to buy.' The role of PEU in shaping PI is significant, particularly when the technology is user-friendly, intuitive and aligns with user behavior. These findings are in agreement with earlier research conducted within the same region [14].

CONCLUSION

Using an Augmented Reality (AR) interface, Shopee offers Virtual Try-On as a way for customers to experience beauty items directly online through simulated reality. By enhancing Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perception Ease of Use (PEU), which are driven by Attitude Toward Using (ATU), Virtual Try-On has been found to significantly increase Purchase Intention (PI) through empirical evidence. The focus of this research is on AR adoption in the beauty product industry of a leading Indonesian e-commerce platform, which provides context-sensitive insights for emerging markets where AR integration in online retail is still in its early stages.

According to the study, Shopee's Virtual Try-On is an easy way for people to shop, acting as a positive initial assessment that leads to more buying. Furthermore, the perceived advantages such as reduced time consumption, enhanced product disclosure, improved decision-support, and increased productivity also reinforce consumers' positive perceptions, which can result in greater purchase behavior. PU is determined by PEU through intuitive learning, clear understanding, intuitive navigation, and feature mastery,

while CU is reinforced when Virtual Try-On offers tangible benefits and is considered valuable.

The study confirms that Virtual Try-On's perceived usefulness, product visualization, interactive nature, and overall user satisfaction are key factors that contribute to purchase decision-making. By establishing these relationships, The study advances our knowledge of how AR-based features influence consumer decision-making in online beauty product purchases.

Future research can build upon this foundation by exploring AR applications across multiple product categories and e-commerce sectors, assessing the long-term impacts on repeat business, brand trust, and customer loyalty. Furthermore, cross-cultural comparative studies could examine how demographic and cultural factors shape AR adoption patterns. These expanded investigations would broaden theorizing about augmented reality in e-commerce and provide practical guidance for integrating AR strategically to create immersive, personalized, and high-conversion shopping experiences.

The data for this research is already available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17033935>.

Angela Berliana Puspita Dewi is the one who collects and processes the data. She also has responsibility to write this paper.

Chyntia Ika Ratnapuri is the supervisor of this paper.

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